

Review

RETRACTED: Embedded Sensors with 3D Printing Technology: Review

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Abstract: Embedded sensors (ESs) are used in smart materials to enable continuous and permanent measurements of their structural integrity, while sensing technology involves developing sensors, sensory systems, or smart materials that monitor a wide range of properties of materials. Incorporating 3D-printed sensors into hosting structures has grown in popularity because of improved assembly processes, reduced system complexity, and lower fabrication costs. 3D-printed sensors can be embedded into structures and attached to surfaces through two methods: attaching to surfaces or embedding in 3D-printed sensors. We discussed various additive manufacturing techniques for fabricating sensors in this review. We also discussed the many strategies for manufacturing sensors using additive manufacturing, as well as how sensors are integrated into the manufacturing process. The review also explained the fundamental mechanisms used in sensors and their applications. The study demonstrated that embedded 3D printing sensors facilitate the development of additive sensor materials for smart goods and the Internet of Things.

Keywords: embedded sensors; 3D printing; inkjet based embedded sensors; sensing mechanism; direct ink writing (DIW); additive manufacturing technique

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1. Introduction

Developing sensors, sensory systems, or smart materials is the focus of sensing technology [1–9]. An embedded sensor (ES) provides continuous and enduring measurements of a structure's structural integrity in smart materials. The integration of ESs was limited to the processing technology used to implant the sensor, although they were sensitive in high temperatures and might be damaged. With streamlined assembly processes, reduced system complexity, and cheaper fabrication costs, 3D-printed sensors are gaining popularity within hosting structures. Two methods can be used to integrate sensors: attaching them to surfaces or embedding them in structures. The first 3D-printed object was created by Hull in 1989 using Stereolithography (SLA). A number of fields, including engineering, manufacturing, biology, and science, have also approved 3D printing. With the development of additive manufacturing, researchers have been able to construct 3D objects with intricate features that were difficult to produce using traditional fabrication techniques. In recent years, embedded 3D printing, an additive manufacturing technique based on material extrusion, has gained a great deal of popularity [10,11]. As opposed to other printing strategies based on the American Society of Testing Materials (ASTM) standard [12], this

printing method allows nozzles to print directly onto “support material” [13]. In contrast to the existing material extrusion process, the new process uses a support matrix with rheological characteristics as the printing medium instead of air. Because shear stress stimulation can break non-covalent and reversible bonds, direct writing can be achieved. When the stimulation is withdrawn and the tip crosses the medium, the medium instantly restores the bond, resulting in ink covering the support material instantly. A support matrix suspends the printed ink due to its rheological characteristics [14]. The hanging structure barely needs assistance before printing. Embedded 3D printing could be support-free, unlike stereolithography and fused deposition modeling. Embedded sensors are a network of devices that are integrated directly into a material. Incorporating them into a host material or physically embedding them is an option [15]. Embedding sensors presents some challenges, including shifts in stress concentrations, crack formation, and increased matrix stiffness, but because the sensors are protected from the external environment, they are less likely to be damaged and more likely to last. In surface-bonded sensors, adhesive is used to attach them to the surface of the host structure. A carefully prepared surface is required to ensure the bonding layer is scaled appropriately to secure the sensor efficiently. There may be a drawback to surface-bonded sensors when it comes to their ability to sense and generate a signal through the bonding layer. This process involves depositing material layer by layer to build a three-dimensional (3D) item from a digital model, known as additive manufacturing (AM), sometimes also called rapid prototyping or 3D printing [16]. Additive manufacturing (AM) has become increasingly popular over the years as a result of its numerous advantages over traditional manufacturing techniques. Compared to conventional methods such as injection molding, plastic forming, CNC machining, and joining plastic, AM technology offers a number of advantages. A number of factors contribute to these advantages, including production cost, speed, quality, and reliability [17,18]. 3D printing is significantly less expensive than conventional technology for small-volume manufacturing where mold development is expensive. In addition to shortening time to market, it ensures quick prototyping and manufacturing. It promotes customization, personalization, and design imagination. In comparison with other manufacturing technologies, additive manufacturing or 3D printing constantly evolves to increase its advantages and benefits [19–21]. Without the correct connection between electrically conductive materials (the communication component) and functional materials (the sensing component), embedded sensing would not work. Multi-material printing enables a fully functional sensor to be fabricated in one step. In comparison with traditional manufacturing methods, which require multiple steps to produce a single sensor and integrate it into a structure, this method was highly advantageous. Unlike conventional technologies, it allowed for a great deal of freedom when it came to developing accessible sensors. AM offers unique advantages over traditional fabrication methods (such as hot pressing, molding, and CNC machines), so it is more likely to be used alongside other techniques than compete against them. It is currently possible to integrate conductive components and functional materials in various ways to facilitate sensing capabilities via additive manufacturing. Combining 3D printing with traditional wiring, printed circuit boards and sensors can be printed [22]. Conductor infusion is another technique that uses 3D printing to print channels in otherwise non-conductive sensing materials and then infuse conductive inks into them [23–25]. Co-printing conductors, or conductive materials, in the same cycle as dielectric materials is one of the most desirable and positive aspects of 3D printing technology [26].

In this review, we discussed different types of embedded sensors and their sensing mechanisms. Furthermore, we discussed several applications of embedded 3D printing sensors in various fields, such as medicine, space, industry, agriculture, and automobiles (Figure 1). Finally, we discussed the challenges and future prospects of embedded sensors using 3D printing.

Figure 1. Different types of 3D-printed embedded sensors and applications in various fields.

2. Approaches to Form Embedded Sensors

Throughout the past few decades, embedded sensors have been studied in structural components, and they have proven to be a dominant technology. However, there are other technologies available, such as fiber optic sensors (FOSs) and piezoelectric sensors (PSs), which are commonly used to develop embedded sensors.

(a) Fiber Optic Sensors (FOSs)

In recent years, fiber optic sensors have become a potential technology for structural elements [27,28]. Utilizing built-in sensors, it is possible to monitor structural characteristics in areas inaccessible to conventional sensors [4,29]. Sensors can also be used to gather information regarding in-service components' functionality and structural integrity or to validate or enhance a project while it is still in the design phase. Because fiber optic sensors are composed of durable materials (such as silica), they can withstand high tensile stresses and corrosion. Additionally, they can elongate up to 5%. Optical wave propagation and physical characteristics form the basis of any fiber optic sensor. Due to different environmental disturbances, these sensors may experience geometrical (size and form) and optical (refractive index and mode conversion) alterations, even though they have optical fibers at their base. To provide smoother and more reliable signals, efforts have been made over the years to reduce these undesirable effects. The use of optical fibers in sensing technology applications has been made possible by these optical alterations that allow for the measurement of external stimuli. As a result of advances in this field, sensitive disturbances in temperature, voltage, rotation, and electrical and magnetic currents can be converted into changes in the optical properties of transmitted light, such as amplitude (intensity), phase, frequency, wavelength, and polarization [30–33]. FOSs are outlined in Table 1, along with the technologies used, the measurements they take, and the optical wave parameters they affect [34,35].

Table 1. Types of optic fiber sensors.

	Point Sensor	Quasi-Distributed Sensor	Distributed Sensor
Sensors	Fabry–Perot Cavity Fiber Bragg Grating Long gage sensor	Fiber Bragg Grating	Raman/Rayleigh Brillouin
Measurands	Strain (displacement, pressure, temperature)	Strain (displacement, acceleration, pressure, relative fissure, inclination, etc.)	Temperature/Strain
Modulation Method	Phase-modulated optical fiber sensors or interferometers	Wavelength	Intensity

The refractive index of an optical fiber with a single mode is modulated permanently and periodically by a Bragg grating. Since it is a quasi-distributed sensor—a Bragg reflector that can reflect light wavelengths while transmitting others—the Fiber Bragg Gratings (FBG) sensor can be multiplexed easily to monitor voltages at multiple locations at the same time. The dielectric wavelength mirror is created by periodically varying the refractive index of the fiber core. Changes in local temperature or voltage affect the wave period and core refraction index, which are followed by measurable changes in the wavelength of reflected light. There are several significant issues raised by the selection of Fiber Bragg Gratings and the monitoring systems that accompany them. As an example, the spectral overlap of gratings modifies nearby wavelengths. Insufficient light or sidebands at the measured wavelength can also lead to errors in the system [30,32,34–37].

For large structures, distributed fiber optic systems are ideal since all fiber optic segments serve as sensors and can measure disturbances inside different areas of the structure. Since this type of sensor relies on modulating light intensity, cracks or other localized structural problems can cause variations in light intensity. There are two important distributed sensor approaches: Optical Time Domain Reflectometry (OTDR) and Brillouin dispersion. Researchers use Rayleigh and Fresnel dispersions and OTDR to monitor structural disturbances. In contrast, Brillouin dispersion displays a measurement-related Doppler shift in light frequency. As distributed sensors have poor resolutions, weak signals, and complex demodulation algorithms, they have not yet seen widespread adoption in civil structures. Despite their innate distributive nature, they have a lot of potential for civil engineering if their challenges are addressed [33,38]. Recent research has explored the use of FOSs in composites and specific metallic components, especially those with low melting points. Fiber optic sensors should be included in these types of structures in a simpler way, in the interest of advancing science.

(b) Piezoelectric Sensors (PSs)

In 1880, the Curie brothers discovered the piezoelectric effect, which Paul Langevin used to produce ultrasounds based on quartz crystal transducers during the First World War. Two examples of groundbreaking developments in piezoelectric ceramics are lead zirconate titanate (PZT) and barium titanate. Furthermore, since they could be sinter-produced, they provided customizable geometries and dimensions, making them more functional than polarized crystals. Due to their numerous applications, PZT-type piezoelectric ceramics dominate the market at the moment. Additionally, PMN ($\text{Pb}(\text{Mg}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3$) and PT (PbTiO_3) are available for devices that require highly specific properties, like high-temperature transducers. In addition to ceramics and quartz crystals, piezoelectric composites, hydrosoluble crystals, piezoelectric mono crystals, piezoelectric semiconductors, and piezoelectric polymers exhibit piezoelectric effects [39].

There is a need for industry to understand the electromechanical behavior of these materials, particularly those that rely on and concentrate on ultrasonics. There is no doubt that piezoelectric ceramics possess the highest degree of shape and flexibility and are widely used in actuators, nondestructive testing, and ultrasound equipment [40]. One of the most promising approaches for the creation of structural health monitoring (SHM) systems

is electromechanical impedance (EMI). This method uses affordable, small piezoelectric sensors and is very simple to implement. Real-world applications of this method have proved challenging, however, and the impact of temperature has been identified as a crucial issue in the literature [41,42]. The low signal-to-noise ratio of highly attenuating materials, easy accessibility to structures, and reproducibility of acoustic coupling are issues with non-destructive ultrasonic inspections. Integrated or connected piezoelectric sensors can be used to track the integrity of a component from the point of manufacture until the end of its life cycle, addressing some of these challenges. Currently, most acoustic and ultrasonic processes use piezoelectric transducers [39,43]. Several metals and composite materials can be incorporated with piezoelectric sensors, according to scientists. Researchers are interested in finding simpler methods of integrating piezoelectric sensors into metal or composite structures.

3. Embedded Sensors with 3D Printing Technology

Various additive manufacturing (AM)/3D printing techniques, like ultrasonic AM, laser powder bed fusion (LPBF), laser cladding (LC), stereolithography (SLA), and fused filament fabrication (FFF), are utilized to investigate embedded sensors. Table 2 summarizes various AM-based 3D printing methods.

(i) Fused filament fabrication (FFF)/Fused deposition modeling (FDM)-based embedded sensors

Most commonly, 3D manufacturing uses fused filament fabrication (FFF) to create parts by extruding material through nozzles and depositing layers of material until a final part is produced (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Schematic view of fused filament fabrication (FFF) [44].

The popularity of this method of manufacturing materials today can be attributed to its ease, affordability, non-toxicity, and economic value. Sensors can be incorporated with FFF by stopping the printing process and integrating them inside the enclosure. For embedded piezoelectric accelerometers, Sbriglia et al. physically inserted sensors and stopped the printing process [45]. Monitoring state-of-health and real-time diagnostics are possible with FFF-embedded sensors. To obtain accurate readings and maximum sensitivity, the sensor must be placed at the optimal depth. Using fine-pitch copper mesh and embedded copper wires, Shemelya et al. developed three different types of capacity sensors. These sensors were incorporated into Aerotech's gantry system [46].

3D printing with FFF technology has shown great promise for producing parts with embedded sensors. A wide range of sensors can be developed using FFF technology, including electrochemical, capacitive, piezoresistive, and piezoelectric sensors. Košir et al.

developed a single-process FFF methodology for producing dynamic piezoelectric sensors. The 3D-printed dynamic sensor was made using four different filaments: thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) (electrode support), heat treat professionals polylactic acid (HTPRO PLA) (build surface), electrify (electrodes), and polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) (piezoelectric film). FFF was used to make the piezoelectric sensor using polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) and poling with an electric field of 16.5 MV/m. As a result of this technique, two types of piezoelectric sensors were manufactured to measure 31 (in-plane—direction along the print trace) and 32 (in-plane—direction perpendicular to 31). The produced charge and the excitation force were used to measure piezoelectric responses in-plane and out-of-plane. Through FFF, Katseli et al. created an electrochemical cell-on-a-chip device. Using a dual extruder 3D printer, a miniature polylactic acid (PLA) cell was made in a single step with three electrodes embedded in carbon-loaded ABS conductive material (Figure 3).

Figure 3. (a) FFF dynamic sensor design in a single process with specified dimensions; (b) for an FFF piezoelectric PVDF film, coordinate the system and mode response directions [46].

The electrochemical sensor is used to test urine contaminated with caffeine (CAF) and paracetamol (PAR) in pharmaceutical pills. Electrolytes with optimal background property and sensitivity for PAR and CAR have been determined to be 0.3 mol/L. A differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) technique was used to measure PAR and CAF simultaneously. Additionally, the design of the electrochemical chip enabled sensitive and quick voltametric analysis using modest amounts of material. In a study by Gooding et al. [47], conductive PLA-graphene composite filaments were used in a 3D-printed strain gauge, which consisted of a rectangular item made with 3DSolutech Natural Clear PLA. In order to measure strain gauge resistance using the conductive material, the bulk resistivity (0.6 cm) and known geometry were used. As soon as the strain gauge is attached to a circuit and supplied with voltage, it deforms and the resistance changes, depending on the geometry and amount of applied stress. When a strain gauge is stressed, the output voltage fluctuation is monitored to determine the sensitivity of the gauge.

An advanced registration technique was developed to capture the moments when the fused deposition modeling machine halted the development of the component, integrated the sensor, and restarted it until the part was completely embedded in polycarbonate material. Wires, meshes, microcontrollers, and light-emitting diodes were embedded as bulk conductive sensors. In order to identify three metallic materials and saltwater from distilled water, these capacitive sensors measured the relative capacitance at ideal depth. Sensors that are embedded in bulk conductive materials are used in biomedical applications, material sensing, electronic characterization, and electrical interconnect characterization. An FDM 3D printer extrudes thermoplastic filament through a nozzle after melting the thermoplastic filament. FDM was first introduced by Crump [48]. In three dimensional (3D) printing, thermoplastic filaments such as polyamide (PA), polylactic acid (PLA), acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), polycarbonate (PC), etc., are commonly used. Due to

its low cost of materials and open-source nature, fused deposition modeling (FDM) has been extensively used, but its slow printing speed and low printing resolution limit its use. 3D printing with FFF/FDM depends on the diameter of the raw materials used to create the object. The two most common standard diameters for materials are 1.75 mm and 2.85 mm, with a few small variations in between. In addition to printing speed, filament extrusion rate, and quantity of material deposited per unit length, the diameter of the raw material influences the printing process. Filament diameter also affects the accuracy and precision of the printed entity [49].

(ii) Stereolithography (SLA)/digital light projection (DLP)-based embedded sensors

A photopolymerization-based 3D printer consists of four different technologies: poly-Jet, digital light projection, stereolithography, and two-photon polymerization [50]. Using a UV laser, SLA creates 3D objects by curing resin layer by layer. UV light is exposed using a projector, also known as a digital light processing unit (DLP). Using micronozzles and UV light, PolyJet jets photopolymer resin droplets while simultaneously curing them. In 2PP, two photons are absorbed simultaneously in a photopolymer substance. A trend toward fabricating embedded electrochemical microfluidic devices (EMDs) and micro-electromechanical systems (MEMSs) will emerge in stereolithography (SLA) 3D printing technology. The light-activated resin was cured layer by layer in a vat using directed irradiation [51]. According to Tse et al., SLA can be used to develop high aspect ratio reaction packages directly on top of MEMS devices [52]. An electrode implanted in a microfluidic device was developed by Costa et al. using stereolithography (SLA). SLA-printed EMDs were demonstrated to be an appropriate substitute tool for coupling separation procedures. In addition to good electrochemical stability, EMD has a high level of conductive activity. As shown in Figure 4, Ragones et al. used SLA to create a stiff mold that was then used to cast a PDMS chip that served as the biosensor's substrate.

Figure 4. (a) Design with negative molds; (b) with SLA technology, a 3D-printed mold; (c) pits and electrode patterns loaded with conductive ink crafted from PDMS; (d) electrodes upon the sputtering of Au; (e) electrodes upon Au electroplating; (f) chip of Au and carbon [53].

Conductive ink was then poured into the trenches created on the casting using the mold as a guide. Figures 5 and 6 showed the development of tactile sensors via DLP

technology, which used conductive ink in printed channels [51]. Hossain et al. also incorporated a flexible RFID temperature memory sensor with no chips into 3D-printed molds [54].

Figure 5. Indirect development of sensors through printed conduits; (a) sensor body in the space of the channels with support material; (b) removal support to create vacant channels; (c) piezoresistive ink injections [46].

Figure 6. Fabrication process of tactile sensor (a) elucidate printing; (b) using microfluidic channels to print on the substrate layer (c) convex structure printing on the cover; (d) sealing and infusing Galinstan [55].

The sensors were produced from many materials at the same time. Initially, a base structure with a microfluidic channel was formed using a photo-sensitive resin substrate. Then, in a resin vat, a distinct photosensitive material was printed to make the channel cover; Figure 6 shows the injection of Galinstan liquid metal into the microchannels following the manufacturing of the 3D-printed part of the sensor. Wang et al. developed 3D-printed functional sensors with incorporated channels through DLP technology, which were injected with Galinstan metal [55].

The applied forces increased successively between 0 N and 10 N under temperatures ranging from 20 °C to 60 °C during the examination of the tactile sensors [55] (Figure 7). Wang et al. also performed 200 cycles with a loading force of 7.5 N and a frequency of 0.08 Hz, lasting 2400 s apiec

Figure 7. Tendencies of tactile sensor: (a) changes in resistance with varying loading factors; (b) resistivity varies with loading frequencies; (c) 200 loading and unloading cycles; (d) testing for heating and cooling cycles [55].

In stereolithography, layers of the model are drawn out or selectively cured using an ultraviolet (UV) laser in a vat of liquid polymer (resin). In this method, a laser beam is aimed across the printing bed using mirrors powered by galvanometers, curing resin point-to-point as it passes. After the first layer is cured, the laser starts curing the next layer, and the printing bed moves up in a top-down system or down in a bottom-up system. It is important to determine the lowest possible laser spot size when determining the resolution of a part. Galvanometer (galvo) systems' resilience and quality can affect the repeatability and resolution of the process. A printer X, Y resolution is correlated with surface finish, edge details and crispness, minimum feature size, and part tolerance (accuracy and precision). In general, SLA systems can achieve an X, Y resolution of 50 μm , a minimum feature size of 150 μm , and an overall tolerance of $\pm 100 \mu\text{m}$, whereas, currently available digital light projection (DLP) systems can typically attain an overall tolerance of $\pm 75 \mu\text{m}$, a minimum feature size of 50–100 μm , and an X, Y resolution of 25–50 μm [56–58].

(iii) Direct Ink Writing (DIW)-based embedded sensors

An extrusion group technique called Direct Ink Writing (DIW), often called Robocasting, was typically employed for non-Newtonian viscous slurry with composite rheological qualities, since it prints at room temperature [59]. The software system, which develops the structure, and the output device, which receives the motion instructions to finish the fabrication process, are the two primary components of equipment used in the DIW method. This method has some special advantages; for the creation of embedded sensor technology, it complements other traditional methods (casting, CNC machining, hot pressing, and molding approaches) rather than competing with them, and it can form a hybrid approach [60]. DIW demonstrates great potential for the development of 3D-printed sensors, with superior functional properties. The transformation of materials with solid-like properties into ink can be applied to metals [61], ceramics [62], wood [63]. Researchers using DIW

expanded globally, moving beyond the field of structural ceramics into other areas, like 3D bioprinting [64], energy [65], sensors [66], and robots [67], etc. A 3D printing technique that can print many components, including conductors [26], piezoelectric/dielectrics [60], flexible [68], and stiff materials [61], is crucial for the 3D printing of sensors [69] because most sensors tend to consist of multiple types of materials. It is possible to produce high-quality, pliable, and consistently sensitive sensors using printable inks [70]. Layered resistance sensors were created using the direct ink writing technique by Vatani et al. [71]. Carbon nano tube inks were used to create the first 3D-printed sensing arrays. To complete the sensors, the 3D-printed portion was encased in polyethylene terephthalate and photocurable resin. Shi et al. prepared high-resolution 3D direct ink writing strain sensors using polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) sub-microbeads/graphene oxide nanocomposite inks. Kim et al. directly printed a glove-type sensor with ten strain gauges to measure finger flexion and extension. The result was a small sensor system that could be manufactured quickly [66]. It is possible to create 3D-printed components with features as small as 250 nm using the direct ink writing method [72].

(iv) Direct Energy Deposition (DED)-based embedded sensors

DED is another AM technology. By scanning a laser beam across a coated targeted surface, a melt pool is generated, and a stream of metallic powder or wire is fed into it (Figure 8) [73]. Polymers, ceramics, and metals comprise some of the material feedstocks employed with DED; however, metals are the most commonly used material in this method, provided as wires or powder [74]. Juhasz et al. introduced a method of printing embedded temperature-resistant strain sensors for metal dog bone specimens using DED [75]. To track temperature degradation and sensor damage, a thick sheet of temperature-resistant material was printed with embedded sensors, and its thickness was adjusted across several trials. One of the main issues that prevented AM embedded sensors from using DED is the protection of the sensor from damage due to laser exposure and temperature changes. The dog bone specimens were 3D printed using a 375 W laser power, 3.23 g/min mass flow rate, 1.7 mm laser spot size, and 1.02 mm layer height. The thickest 3D-printed strain gauge sensor was the only one fabricated through the DED process and could generate an output response when tensile stress was applied.

Figure 8. Illustration of a laser-powered DED process [46].

(v) Laser powder bed fusion (LPBF)-based embedded sensors

One of the most prevalent AM techniques is laser powder bed fusion (LPBF), in which powder is melted and fused using a laser. A variety of metals, such as Inconel, titanium, and stainless steel, as well as polymers, such as nylon, were typically used [76]. Standardization of LPBF embedding sensors was introduced by Binder et al. [77]. In terms of embedded sensing, LPBF has a few challenges in terms of ensuring a safe environment for the sensor (such as high temperatures, high pressures, powder contamination, chamber dimensions, inert gas flows, and the powder coater). With an elastic casting compound, the PT100 temperature sensor was protected from electrostatics and powder contamination, while maintaining precise measurements. All sensors were operational after embedding, but the delayed reaction was caused by the embedding's isolative effect. To protect the sensor from direct laser radiation, an aluminum cover was fitted. Stoll et al. introduced innovative non-destructive testing techniques for monitoring SS 316 by utilizing embedded eddy current (EC) sensors [78]. Using embedded ECs, it was demonstrated that crack propagation could be tracked and the extent of the damage assessed over an extended period. Magnetic fields are a mainstay of EC operation principles, which are based on the use of SS 316. This material has a low magnetic permeability, matching EC operation principles that require the use of magnetic fields. The sensor was systematically embedded into the CAD model using the AM process, and after selective laser melting (SLM), the cavity was filled with the sensor. As shown in Figures 9 and 10, the cavity filled with resin after the sensor was pressed against the bottom surface of the cavity for sensor integration. Raw materials in LPBF are typically powders with particle sizes ranging from 10 to 60 microns. LPBF is characterized by a thin layer of powder deposited on a build plate by a spreader [79].

Figure 9. (a) CAD representation of the prototype with a specifically designed cavity for EC sensor integration; (b) schematic diagram of the prototype before crack development; (c) schematic diagram of the prototype depicting crack progression towards the embedded sensor [78].

SS 316 embedded sensors were developed by Havermal et al. to compare bare SS 316 samples and measure strain levels, plastic deformation, and elastic deformation [78]. By embedding the sample in the substrate through a groove in the part, nickel-coated Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors detect the motion of the sample. In the initial cycles, the sample was plastically deformed but not in subsequent cycles. Long-term elastic stability was investigated using the sensor. To minimize sensor response time, H. Hyer and C.

Petrie used SS 316 powders to embed an optical sensor and a thermocouple to measure strain. To sense strain, the optical sensor needed nearly perfect embedding, while the embedded thermocouple's surface roughness and gaps should be minimized [80]. A strain and temperature response is crucial for determining the results. In the embedded region, strain response is well-observed; adequate bonding is also observed. Even though the embedded sensor's heating rate was different from the bare sensor's, Figure 11 showed that the embedded sensor reached the same temperature as the bare sensor. Despite having approximately the same amount of noise, embedded and bare sensors share the same vibrational detection accuracy (Figure 12), although bare sensors lack control parameters. Jung et al. described that the IC is Bluetooth-enabled, with a connection range exceeding 100 m.

Figure 10. Procedure for integrating EC sensors: (a) removal of powder, placing heat-shrink tubes within protect wires, and passing wires through tubes; (b) cavity incorporation of the EC sensor; (c) specimens for the LPBF with soldered cables [78].

Figure 11. Temperature sensor operation processed by SE-SLM is validated by comparing data with a bare temperature sensor: (a) monitoring the in situ temperature of SE-SLM SUS316L using data reading configuration; (b) comparison of temperatures; (c) curve of temperature increase slope; (d) comparison of noise levels [81].

Figure 12. IC component based on PCB embedded in metal: (a) configuration of an IC chip inserted in a metal component; (b) Inconel 718 turbine vane integrated into an IC chip; (c) turbine vane temperature monitored wirelessly; acceleration data recorded for every vibration input axis (d) X-axis, (e) Y-axis, (f) Z-axis [81].

(vi) Inkjet-based embedded sensors

By using piezoelectric inkjet technology, inkjet 3D printers release material droplets onto a bed; each layer is healed before the next layer is deposited. There are two types of inkjet printing: drop-on-demand printing (DoD) and continuous inkjet printing (CIJ) [82]. These technologies led to the development of two multi-material technologies: polyjet (Stratasys Objet Geometries Co., Rehovot, Israel) (Figure 13a) and multijet (3D Systems) (Figure 13b).

Figure 13. Schematic diagram of (a) multijet; (b) polyjet printing [46].

Both technologies employed micronozzles to jet liquid plastic materials, casting wax materials, or photopolymer resin droplets while simultaneously curing them with UV light [83]. In those technologies, print heads are supported by gel-like materials. Printheads in multijet were limited to two, whereas printheads in polyjet could be two or more. Andà et al. developed a flexible electromagnetic actuator using a low-cost inkjet printer [84,85]. Through additive manufacturing, they built a conductive coil onto a PET substrate and attached an external magnet to it. Additionally, a strain gauge was 3D printed onto the PET beam and connected with a coil and magnet to the patterned printed circuit board. With the help of polyjet technology, Pinto et al. developed a rapid manufacturing method of

microfluidic substrates embedded with liquid metals [86,87]. Guo et al. explained a simple method for fabricating microfluid strain sensors widely used in lab-on-chip devices for strain and pressure measurement using inkjet printing [88]. In addition, they explained that 3D printing opened a new era for the development of soft robotic sensors. Microfluidic sensors are made by 3D printing, which reduces the cost of materials and saves time. The goal of this study is to examine the behavior of a mesoscale inkjet-printed accelerometer in the low-frequency domain (up to 20 Hz), which is well-suited for common applications in seismic and human monitoring. Four spring legs hold a polyethylene terephthalate membrane to a fixed support [89]. An inkjet-printed polymeric accelerometer with SU-8 material deposition was described by Roberto et al. The optimized device has a resolution of 2×10^{-3} g, a sensitivity of 6745 nm/g, and an acceleration range of 0–0.7 g. Based on these characteristic properties, inkjet printing can be used for a wide range of applications requiring accurate acceleration measurements across small displacements [90]. The low-cost magnetic field sensor prototype was also explained by Bruno et al. A magnetic field range of 0–27 mT, a device responsivity of 3700/T, and a resolution of 0.458 mT were investigated [91]. Commercially available piezo-based inkjet printers have made it possible to print RF structures with 20 m features. Inkjet printers based on electro hydrodynamics can produce features smaller than 1 mm in size [92].

(vii) Hybrid additive manufacturing technology

The speed at which additive manufacturing produces goods, especially in large quantities, prevents it from being used profitably. As a result, hybrid procedures are concluded by contemporary research, which include the integration of additive processes into the regular industrial production process [93–95]. Additive manufacturing requires a repeatable process due to its sequential nature. With liquid metal lattice materials, Deng et al. created re-configurable lattice hands [96]. Combining DLP 3D printing with carbon nanotube (CNT) ultrasonication coating, Yin et al. created a programmable lattice pressure sensor [97]. In stereolithography (SLA) technology and dip coating, Kamat et al. created a piezoresistive pressure sensor containing graphene nanoplatelets [98]. Different metallic and alloy coatings are deposited using electroless plating (ELP), including copper, silver, gold, nickel-phosphorus alloy, etc. A 3D substrate is also a preferred complementary technology for manufacturing 3D electronics in hybrid additive manufacturing [99–101]. To determine the ELP deposition area for 3D electronics, Hensleigh et al. used SLA printing to create a dual-material structure using positive, negative, and neutral resins, which were then soaked in positive or negative catalyst solutions [102]. Using DLP and ELP procedures to deposit metal layers on the micro-lattice, Shin et al. increased the lattice's compressive rigidity from 8.8 MPa to 11.1 MPa [103]. To fabricate high-resolution 3D conformal/embedded circuit boards, sensors, antennas, etc., Liu et al. integrated laser-activated ELP with a variety of AM technologies [104–108].

Table 2. Summary of AM-based 3D printing methods and materials.

Printing Technology	AM Based 3D Printing Methods	Materials	Performance of Materials	References	
Extrusion-based printing	Fused deposition modeling (FDM)	Thermoplastics e.g., PLA, ABS, nylon	The filament was melted and extruded through a high-temperature nozzle that was used for 3D translation.	[13]	
	3D Inkjet	Ultraviolet (UV) curable and low viscous materials	Viscosity is crucial in 3D printing. It affects the quality of the printed object and speed of the printing process. Low viscosity materials require lower extrusion temperatures and fast printing speeds.	[109,110]	
	Direct ink writing (DIW)	Elastomers, thermosets, metals, and ceramics in micro/nano particle solutions and biomaterials	It can print materials at room temperature and in an ambient environment. Inks were formulated to exhibit shear-thinning and yield rheological behaviors, which are desired to be extruded smoothly and also maintain their shapes after extrusion.	[111,112]	
Liquid resin-based printing	Stereolithography (SLA)	Light (UV, LEDs, or laser) curable polymers	To create a solid layer, a UV laser is used to locally cure the resin along the printing routes or projected patterns. SLA uses a point-source laser light beam, but DLP increases printing speed by projecting pictures across the entire platform at each layer.	[113,114]	
	Direct light processing (DLP)			[115]	
Powder-based printing	Selective laser sintering (SLS)	Metal and alloys, polymers, and semiconductors	The particles are locally melted and fused together using a high-energy laser beam to create 3D geometry layer by layer. The platform is lowered after each layer is created, and fresh powder is added to print the subsequent layer.	[116]	
	Direct energy deposition (DED)			For melting wire-based or powder-based filler materials, a high-energy beam is employed. It can be utilized in tandem with other subtractive manufacturing techniques and for repair reasons.	[117]
	Laser powder bed fusion (LPBF)			In it, a laser is used to melt and fuse powder.	[114]

4. Sensing Mechanism

The main aim of sensing technology is to develop sensors, sensory systems, and smart materials that detect a wide range of structural component qualities. Various sensors are available for industrial applications. Sensors can also improve processes and provide significant protection to industrial equipment or components for more demanding industrial applications [118]. Using sensors, we can quantify the physical, chemical, or biological properties of materials, converting them into signals that can be measured by appropriate equipment, as shown in Figure 14. Considering ST's continuous development and its new developments, it is noteworthy that sensors can be divided into two categories: Surface Sensors (SSs) and Embedded Sensors (ESs). The difference between the two types of sensors is illustrated in Figure 15.

Figure 14. Sensing mechanism [118].

Figure 15. Monitoring sensor implementation: (a) surface sensors; (b) embedded sensors [118].

Figure 16 illustrates two techniques for monitoring a component: passive monitoring and active monitoring. Any of these outcomes can be achieved by sensors. Passive monitoring relies on the physical properties of the component under inspection, such as piezoelectricity, pyroelectricity, and thermoelectricity, etc., since interactions with the component throughout its life cycle result in variations in the properties that provide information for the analysis [119,120]. Active monitoring involves embedding or mounting sensors to capture responses triggered by stimuli. An embedded actuator provides information for analysis through the application of stimuli. In applications involving the monitoring of structural integrity, signal sensors (SSs) are most used. They work by transmitting electrical impulses. Over the past 20 years, however, significant advancements have been made in the field of FOSs, despite their sensitivity to magnetic or electrical interference. FOSs provide a more advantageous option for the inspection of SHM systems and upcoming smart structures compared to conventional technologies. There is a rapid development of embedded sensors (ESs) at present. A thin-film piezoelectric sensor is

used in composite aircraft components, described by Wang et al. In a more comprehensive analysis, Janeliukstis et al. analyzed the technological limits of using piezoelectric sensors and fiber optic sensors in composite components [121]. Through the development of smart materials and the integration of systems into structural components, new mechanisms emerged, posing challenges to the development of smart structural components.

Figure 16. Methods for component monitoring with embedded sensors: (a) passive; (b) active monitoring [118].

4.1. Types of Sensing Mechanisms

4.1.1. Transducing

Sensors consist of transducers, interpreters, and detecting components [122]. A sensing mechanism can be classified on a physical or chemical basis. In the following sections, we discuss the features of several transduction mechanisms to determine which sensing element would be suitable for various applications.

(i) Piezoresistivity

Electrical resistivity changes are interpreted by piezoresistive devices when electromechanical systems are subjected to mechanical strain [123]. Devices are used in piezoresistive devices that can incorporate or connect electrodes (Figure 17a). Piezoresistive sensors should be electrically conductive to achieve accurate sensor readings and minimize the effect of structural, mechanical, and electrical factors on their performance. Using 3D-printed stretchable and porous sensing elements, Wang et al. addressed common piezoresistive challenges, such as signal sensitivity [124]. Carbon black nanoparticles and sodium chloride sacrificial particles provided porosity for the sensing layer, but plastic urethane and silver flakes provided electrode printing ink.

(ii) Capacitance

Capacitive sensors are made up of two parallel electrode plates sandwiched between dielectric material [125] (Figure 17b). A force applied to a sensor directly affects the distance between the capacitor plates, and capacitance is measured as a function of the area covered by those plates. Using 3D printing, Qiu et al. developed integrated sensing capacitors to create tissues and organs for surgical preparation [126]. When the tactile sensor deformed, a capacitance shift occurred that correlated precisely with applied pressure, simulating the handling of organs and tissues during surgery.

(iii) Piezoelectricity

One of the most effective transduction techniques in terms of output voltage and high sensitivity is piezoelectricity, which converts applied mechanical energy into a voltage or creates an electric current (Figure 17c) [127]. Piezoelectric material (such as lead zirconate

titanate (PZT), barium titanate (BT), or polyvinylidene fluoride) is placed between two electrodes to form the piezoelectric transducer (PVDF). The use of 3D printing made it possible to print complex geometries with strong piezoelectric efficiency, allowing for the functionalization of additively manufactured parts. Cui et al. prepared PZT colloidal particles for implementation into photo-sensitive ink to produce 3D-printed complex architectures [128]. The order of complete piezoelectric device manufacturing is as follows: 3D printing fabrication, electrode formation, and poling. Figure 17 illustrates three popular transduction methods. 3D printing allows the merging of the first two phases and facilitates electrode generation and poling [16].

Figure 17. Schematic diagram of three common transduction methods: (a) piezoresistivity; (b) capacitance; (c) piezoelectricity [129].

(iv) Magnetic sensing

Using 3D printing technology, functional magnetic sensor devices of complex geometries can be manufactured with various materials and scales [69]. A magnetic sensor detects the presence of a magnetic field and provides pertinent information about a substance's position, speed, rotation, and direction. Credi et al. 3D printed highly sensitive magnetically responsive cantilever beams and confirmed their viability as magnetic sensors [130]. Huber et al. combined permanent magnetic filaments with pure polyamide (PA12) filaments to produce 3D-printed polymer-bonded magnets with variable magnetic compound fractions [131].

4.1.2. Wired

In addition to wiring, printed circuit boards, or sensors, electronic functionality was added to simultaneously created devices [132]. In 3D printing sensor technology, the sensor is embedded into a printed structure; it is printed. Wired embedded sensors can be created by printing conductive and non-conductive materials simultaneously or by linking non-conductive materials with conductive inks through previously printed channels [26]. By fusing deposition modeling with embedded wiring, Shemelya et al. successfully produced encapsulated capacitive sensors [46]. Embedded sensors could be easily fabricated; first, the nonconductive part was manufactured, and then, the electronic component was attached. To embed all electronic components completely, the additive manufacturing (AM) process was repeatedly interrupted. Before the joint-angle sensor could be 3D printed, the manufacturing process had to be stopped after the wire harness cavity was built to add the aforementioned component. In order to maintain accuracy during printing, the process had to be arranged and registered, since the printing process would have to be paused several times during the development of the sensor. To fabricate embedded sensors, conductive materials could be fused through channels in non-conductive printed parts; however, this

method is challenging because the insertion and removal of supports in narrow areas is difficult due to the fusion of materials. Chizari et al. used AM autonomy to synthesize more conductive PLA/CNT nanocomposites for 3D printing liquid sensors [133].

Using an extruder, the material could be tunable in scaffold thickness, which inversely affected the relative resistance change. Deformation caused by solvent evaporation during printing led to filament overlap and, consequently, more sensitive sensors. Design freedom and ease of production are provided by multi-material printing, which fuses materials to create sensors. 3D printing technologies based on ink or paste, such as direct ink write (DIW), are commonly used to fabricate sensors. Unlike earlier methods, multi-material printing allows fabrication of the sensor in a single print, without interrupting or halting fabrication during the print process. Using Glass bend Flexi material and silver palladium paste, a bendable smart sensing structure can be 3D printed [134]. Multi-material printing allows fabrication of the sensor in a single print without interrupting fabrication in the middle of the process, as opposed to earlier methods. For all of these techniques, wired embedded sensors face the challenge of needing to be physically connected by a wire to both a power source and the component that will be producing the data. A new technology emerged that makes it possible to develop wireless sensors using AM.

4.1.3. Wireless

Embedded printed components can detect pressure, temperature, motion, and other physical and environmental characteristics, making them effective wireless sensors for precise sensing, computing, and communication [135]. Wu et al. developed a passive wireless inductor-capacitor (LC) tank sensor that measured the shift in resonance frequency after 36 h at room temperature [136]. Afterwards, liquid metal paint was used to create electrically conductive coils, channels, and pads. Researchers have investigated the use of 3D printing to create wireless implantable sensors today. Researchers developed a wireless, stretchable implantable biosystem that could be used to monitor cerebral aneurysm hemodynamics in real-time through biological tissue up to 6 cm in length using 3D printing [137]. Kalthori et al. designed and 3D printed a small LC location sensor that allows readouts up to 10 cm away using improved wireless capabilities [138]. Additionally, 3D-printed soft capacitive strain sensors were integrated with wireless vascular stents, providing a biocompatible, battery-free, and wireless monitoring system. An adaptable wireless implantable neural probe was created by Parker et al. using 3D printing technology [139].

5. Design Considerations of 3D-Printed Sensors

In comparison to subtractive manufacturing, additive manufacturing, also known as 3D printing, is more affordable because less material is used, and it can produce complex shapes [140]. There are numerous additive manufacturing (AM) processes available to make various materials, including stereo-lithography (SLA), selective laser sintering (SLS), and fused filament fabrication (FFF) [141]. In the late 1980s, Guo and Leu developed a technique called fused deposition modeling or FFF [142]. The FDM method is a quick method of prototyping complex geometric parts [142,143]. Computer-guided deposition of molten feedstock material is the basis of the FDM method, according to Cantrell et al. [144]. The FDM process comprises adding and connecting materials without the use of templates or molds, according to Chen et al. [145]. The FDM process is increasingly used to create specialized products for engineering and medical applications, according to Brenken et al. [140]. A 3D build platform usually moves vertically along the Z-axis, with the X- and Y-axes lying horizontally [146]. A semi-liquid material is extruded from the original filament in a predetermined pattern through a heated nozzle onto a platform to create the target pieces [147]. As the material cools and solidifies, it forms a link with the material next to it [148]. Complex geometries can require support material to create geometric overhangs [140]. Multiple nozzles can deposit various materials in more intricate systems, according to Guo and Leu [142].

Polyurethane (TPU) and polylactic acid (PLA) are the most popular thermoplastics [149]. It is generally accepted that biodegradable polymers are more environmentally friendly than conventional polymers. The PLA polymer is made from sugar, corn, potatoes, and other renewable resources. It belongs to the aliphatic polyester family [149,150]. PLA is a thermoplastic polyester that is non-toxic and biodegradable. A modest shrinkage rate and a relatively low melting point (160–170 °C) have been reported by Fernández-Vicente and Conejero [151]. As it is biocompatible with living tissues, it can be used to construct structures, capsules, and scaffolds for bone growth [152]. In addition to removing the need for implant removal, PLA decomposition typically produces carbon dioxide and water, which the body can naturally eliminate. These qualities have made PLA a common material for FDM 3D printing, according to Dal Maso and Cosmi [153]. Pure PLA material, however, has a limited range of applications due to its mechanical limitations [149]. According to Tao et al., PLA is regarded as brittle and has low toughness, impact strength, and flexibility [154].

As a versatile and reasonably easy manufacturing process, FDM appeals to many industries. In reconstructive surgery, bioresorbable implants can assist [155], and scaffolds with specifically engineered geometrical properties can stimulate cell proliferation [145]. By 3D printing highly flexible sensors into devices, wearable electronics, human-machine interfaces, and soft robotics can be integrated with soft functional materials. FDM can be used to customize prosthetic limbs; however, Tao et al. emphasize that it is difficult to design one design that meets the needs of various applications [156].

The production of functional products must consider the mechanical properties of 3D-printed parts [143]. Using traditional methods (such as homogenous injection molding) typically results in different mechanical properties than those made using 3D printing, according to Song et al. and Kim et al. [157,158]. In most cases, FDM parts are used only when minimal mechanical loading is required [148]. However, by modifying the design and printing process, one can influence the mechanical characteristics of 3D-printed lightweight cellular composite structures, including their strength and elastic properties [159]. It is important to take into account changes in printing orientation, layer height, material type, printing speed, number of perimeter walls, infill pattern, raster angle, density, air gap sizes, and printing temperatures when trying to control the properties of 3D-printed parts. According to Pahonie et al. [160], varying mesh density affects the mechanical characteristics of 3D-printed ABS and PLA specimens for orthotic devices. It was found that changing mesh densities for various orthotic device parts (insoles) could help reduce foot stress by up to 25% when off-lead. Using computational and experimental methods, Qattawi et al. investigated how various processing factors affect the mechanical characteristics and dimensional accuracy of 3D-printed objects [161]. Separate analyses were conducted for each of these parameters. Their findings indicate that mechanical characteristics are not significantly affected by printing speed or infill pattern, due to the down-sizing geometry of the specimens. However, increasing the infill percentage resulted in improved mechanical performance. To increase the dimensional accuracy of 3D-printed parts, it is necessary to modify the extrusion temperature, the layer height, and the construction direction. According to Kim et al., a comparison of the tensile strength of PLA and ABS based on orientation angle, infill rate, and material type shows that PLA prints with 100% infill have ideal mechanical properties [159]. In addition, the structural design of numerous material sections can improve the mechanical properties, even with a constant materials ratio.

6. Application

According to different fabrication methods and mechanisms, 3D printing embedded sensors have shown various applications (Table 3), as follows:

(i) Biosensor

A biosensor measures biological reactions by producing a proportional signal to analyte concentration [162]. Biosensors include a bioreceptor, a molecule identifying the substance to be detected, and a transducer, which converts the bioreaction into an electrical

reaction displayed on an electrical display. AM offers many advantages in relation to this phenomenon, including design freedom, quick production for point-of-care testing, and fine features at the microscale. Among the most prominent biosensors are the rapid dengue and COVID-19 tests. Different types of Dengue viruses need to be identified because DENV-2 or DENV-3 may cause life-threatening illness. Suvanasuthi et al. demonstrated a 3D-printed biosensor that detects and distinguishes dengue virus serotypes [163]. To print a sensor incorporated into a structure, researchers used two different printing techniques: material extrusion and vat photopolymerization. In order to construct the fluidic chip, vat photopolymerization was utilized. Material extrusion was used to print PLA and wax microfluidic paper-based analytical devices. These sensors are based on RNA toehold switches, where the triggers are embedded in 3D-printed sheets, and the switch binds sequences of each dengue virus serotype. The fluidic chip prevents the sample from flowing to the absorption pads in order to allow enough time for the reaction. This simple enclosure is designed, as shown in Figure 18. According to Figure 19, the sensors showed a high degree of specificity when it came to distinguishing between the serotypes.

Figure 18. Schematic diagram of dengue virus serotype biosensor prototype: (a) prototype consists of fluidic chip component; (b) the reaction zone (yellow mesh area) pushed up against the reaction cover (white mesh area) by the press structure [46].

Figure 19. Specificity of RNA toehold switches in cell-free reactions for dengue virus serotype detection [46].

(ii) Chemical Sensor

Similar to biosensors, chemical sensors are also based on the interaction between the analyte and receptor, which is translated into an electrical signal. Chemical sensors, however, detect chemical information rather than biological information. Chemical sensors were commonly used in breathalyzers and home carbon monoxide detectors [85]. Using 3D printing and assembly, Bao et al. developed an integrated neuromorphic sensor that replicates sensing in an organism. The sensor, oscillator, and transistor were all manufactured together. Several printing techniques were required for this sophisticated system, from material extrusion for the substrates to direct ink writing for the inductors, capacitors, and resistors. In soils, it can detect ion concentrations and identify low nutrient concentrations. The system started by monitoring soil K^+ ion concentrations [164]. Figure 20 illustrates the three layers of the integrated system: inductors, capacitors, and resistors.

Figure 20. Characterization of 3D-embedded electrical oscillator. (a) A circuit equivalent to the Colpitts oscillator; (b) schematic diagram of 3D-embedded electrical oscillator; (c) fabrication process (i) manufactured on the printed substrate initially, then the intermediate layer of inductors, (ii) the superior resistors, (iii) a 3D integrated LC Colpitts oscillator; (d) 3D-printed oscillator; (e) LTspice simulation of AC signal; (f) experimental result from 3D oscillator [164].

(iii) Gas Sensor

Due to the increasing health concerns associated with dangerous gases, it is crucial to develop gas sensors that are sensitive to certain gases. There are several applications for gas sensing, including controlling indoor and outdoor air quality, ensuring national security, and controlling chemical processes in factories [165]. A basic sensing process involves gas adsorption-induced charge transfer [166] and doping [77]. The mechanism of gas-sensing materials, such as metal oxides, has been extensively studied and well-described. A precise integrated joule heating element was used to achieve the best selectivity and sensitivity performance from commercial metal oxide sensors. Khan and Briand developed a fully printed metal-oxide gas sensor using aerosol jets and inkjets. As compared to conventional metal-oxide gas sensors, the all-printed metal-oxide gas sensor obtained acceptable chemoresistive responses for CO and NO_2 [167]. This work illustrates future applications of metal oxide gas sensors in disposable systems and portable smart-printed electronics.

(iv) Piezoresistive Sensor

Sensors with piezoresistive characteristics were the most widely used in micro- and macrosystems. In order for them to operate, mechanical stress had to be applied, which altered the electrical resistance of the material [168]. These types of sensors use semiconductors, such as silicon, germanium, and polymers, with piezoresistive properties. Typically, these materials are used in microelectromechanical system (MEM) devices, such as pressure sensors, microfluidic devices, and accelerometers, where the substrate is a rigid silicon. Pagliano et al. developed a functional MEM accelerometer using two-photon polymerization and metal evaporation. Due to the bending of 3D-printed cantilevers, the metal strain gauges flexed, which in turn changed their electrical resistance [169]. Piezoresistive sensors were effectively mimicked by this accelerometer. In order to achieve this, substitute materials, primarily composites such as metal nanoparticle infusions and carbon-based inclusions have been developed. The ability to develop flexible piezoresistive sensors additively proved useful in several areas. A few examples of applications are wearable electronics [51], airflow sensors [170], food monitoring [171], embedded pressure sensors in tires [172], and pneumatic actuators [173]. A 3D-printed flexible piezoresistive pressure sensor was developed by Fekiri et al. using polydimethylsiloxane and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT-PDMS composite) and direct ink write AM (Figure 21) [174]. Moreover, 3D-printed sensors were attached to non-conforming surfaces to demonstrate their flexibility and bendability [169]. Various technologies have been advanced through the use of piezoresistive sensors, as demonstrated by their successful applications. Using compact, affordable parts, piezoresistive sensors convert mechanical changes into electrical resistance changes and produce electrical signals.

Figure 21. 3D-printed MWCNT-PDMS material on soft substrate: (a) extremely flexible and bendable 3D-printed material demonstrations in practical applications, sensor connected to non-conformal surfaces; (b) 3D-printed stretchable serpentine shape; (c) 3D-printed grid; (d) MWCNT-PDMS composite on non-conformal surface [174].

(v) Inertial Sensor

Sensors relying on inertia and relevant measurement methods are known as inertial sensors. Inertial sensors and acceleration sensors, both of which have a maximum size of 50 cm, and Micro Electro-Mechanical System (MEMS) inertial sensors are very small [175]. In MEMS gyros, a mass held in place by a spring is constantly vibrated, similar to acceleration sensors in some ways. By applying angular velocity (vibrating gyroscope) to the mass, Coriolis force is produced. Due to the small mass of a MEMS device, inertial forces are also very small, particularly the Coriolis force. As a result, together with the mechanical structure design, the circuit design should also measure the mass movement triggered by critical forces. Recently, MEMS inertial sensors with integrated circuits have been developed, putting the entire sensor assembly on a single chip.

(a) Acceleration Sensor

In this area, on-chip digital signal processing, three-dimensional sensing, cost reduction, and additional miniaturization are key. MEMS acceleration sensors are widely available on the market and are well-integrated into many mass-produced products, includ-

ing cell phones, PDAs, game consoles, pedometers, and automobiles. Currently, MEMS acceleration sensors are quite visible. In recent years, on-chip digital signal processing, three-dimensional sensing, and cost reduction have become increasingly important. In addition to cell phones, PDAs, game consoles, pedometers and fitness meters, MEMS acceleration sensors are well-integrated into numerous mass-produced products. The device resolution is often restricted to approximately $0.1 \text{ mg Hz}^{-1/2}$, due to the small mass and displacement [176].

(b) Gyroscopes

In recent years, silicon MEMS gyroscopes have been introduced into the market. In a basic construction similar to acceleration sensors, a mass is supported by springs. A primary operational distinction is the measurement of the Coriolis force exerted on the vibrating mass to determine the angular velocity. Therefore, mass mobility should have at least two degrees of freedom. While spring K_y permits movement of the inner part of the structure in the y direction, spring K_x allows movement of the entire structure in the x direction. A comb-style actuator located at its center causes the apparatus' interior mass to vibrate in the y direction. The inner mass experiences an x -direction Coriolis force, which causes the entire structure, including the outer section, to move x -wise. At the moment, the resolution of MEMS gyroscopes is $0.01\text{--}0.1 \text{ deg s}^{-1} \text{ Hz}^{-1/2}$. Zero-point stability is a significant flaw in MEMS gyros. This is because it is challenging to measure the tiny displacement that the Coriolis force produces. Temperatures reaching hundreds of degrees Celsius are frequently reached [176].

Table 3. Fabrication, mechanism, and application of 3D printing embedded sensors.

Methods	Material	Mechanism	Strength	limitation	Application	Refs.
FFF	TPU/PLA/Carbon black; Polyphenylsulfone/Polycarbonate	Capacitive	Simple use and maintenance, easy to assemble, low cost.	Poor quality; lack of structural integrity, low resolution	Biomedical sensing, tactile sensing, material sensing	[26,177]
DIW	Graphene/PDMS; PTFE/PDMS/TPU/Carbon black;	Piezoresistive; electrical resistive	Allows customized materials; low material consumption, open source of controlling; feasible for multilateral printing.	Introduction of massive materials into 3D architecture design.	Skin-attachable electronics, smart textile	[55,178]
LPBF	SS316L powder (Conductive material)	Magnetic	Tensile strength and compressive yield strength of 669.92 ± 18.68 MPa and 75.65 ± 5.77 MPa, respectively.	Relatively slow, long print time; long build time due to power preheating and cooling-off periods; slowest additive manufacturing processes.	Structural health monitoring	[77]
SLM	SUS 316L, Inconel 718C	Thermal	High energy density; ultimate tensile strength of 500 MPa–1100 MPa; hardness 25 HRC–39 HRC; and 10–25% percentage elongation.	High in cost; extensive post processing to achieve desired surface; increased material usage.	Self-cognitive ability of metals	[78]
SLA	PDMS; optical fiber	Electrochemical; pulse-calling	Creates complex geometry; printed with tough resin; 55.7 MPa tensile strength; 2.7 GPa elasticity.	Limited number of materials used in stereolithography due to nature of curing; expensive in cost.	Biological sensing	[47,78]
Inkjet	ZnO, Acrylic rubber	Resistive	Low cost; high-quality output; prints fine and smooth; easy to use; fast speed; high-quality images.	Long span of time; print heads are clogged.	Robotics	[179,180]
FDM	TPU/graphite ink; BTO/MWCNT/PVDF; PLA/wax filament	Capacitive, piezoelectric	Affordable; works with many materials; easy modeling; relatively fast.	Poor mechanical properties; average manufacturing accuracy; single colour model, slow manufacturing process.	Robotics, Dengue virus sensing, energy storage	[66,132,181]

7. Challenges and Future Prospects

It is generally acknowledged that any sensor or monitoring system faces challenges when it comes to achieving high structural reliability, such as detecting damage precisely. As a result of AM, embedded sensors offer several advantages, including cost reductions, faster production, and customizability. The rapid development of 3D printing poses several challenges, however. The printing process and material selection need to be carefully controlled to ensure accurate and repeatable sensing performance from 3D-printed sensors, for example. Choosing the right material for 3D printing sensors that require mechanical and electrical properties can also be challenging. 3D-printed sensors may be limited in their application due to their limitations in terms of sensitivity and response time as compared to conventional sensors. In addition, 3D-printed sensors might lose their performance over time as they age or are exposed to extreme conditions.

Despite these challenges, 3D-printed embedded sensors have a bright future because new materials are being developed that are more durable and perform better. 3D printing has reduced the cost of producing sensors and increased their utility by eliminating the need for specialized machinery and tools. It is expected that 3D-printed integrated sensors will become more accurate and reliable as 3D printing technology develops. As a result of the ability to customize 3D printing, it was possible to develop sensors with unique and special functionality, thereby expanding the possibilities of 3D-printed embedded sensors. The use of 3D printing also made it possible for new sensors to be launched at a faster rate. As embedded sensors become more popular, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) techniques are being used to enhance their performance. In the future, AI and machine learning algorithms will be able to analyze a vast amount of data collected by 3D-embedded sensors and identify trends that are not immediately apparent to humans. Integrated sensors are also benefiting from the increasing use of wireless communication technology; many of these sensors are now able to receive and transmit data wirelessly, allowing for real-time monitoring and analysis. For example, industrial automation or environmental monitoring applications may not be able to physically connect sensors to a centralized data gathering system. Despite their limited obstacles, 3D-printed embedded sensors have bright prospects and have the potential to completely transform the sensor market.

As a result of previous studies and the working hypotheses, the authors should discuss the results and how they can be interpreted. It is important to discuss the findings and their implications in a broader context. Research directions for the future should also be discussed.

8. Conclusions

Here, in this review, we discuss 3D-printed embedded sensors in great detail. We have assessed various 3D printing techniques for sensor integration and application domains, as well as conducted a comprehensive analysis of various materials and their 3D printing processes. In the future, 3D printing with sensors may offer many interesting possibilities. The addition of 3D-printed sensors to robots and AI systems can improve their sensory capabilities, making them more flexible, intelligent, and responsive. In medical implants and devices that monitor vital signs and track the healing process, 3D-printed sensors can deliver targeted medications. It is possible to use 3D-printed sensors to collect data on temperature, humidity, air quality, and other environmental variables in remote or difficult-to-reach locations. Sensors printed on 3D printers enable real-time data collection and transmission for a variety of Internet of Things (IoT) applications, including industrial automation and smart homes. Future applications for 3D-printed sensors are likely to become much more inventive as technology advances. In addition, they can be incorporated into materials and constructions to measure their performance and gather vital information for design and optimization.

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